

Synthesis of Some Basic N-4-Arylthiazolyl and N-4(Substituted) Arylthiazolyl Butyramides as Potential Local Anaesthetics

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Some new basic N-4-arylthiazolyl and N-4 (substituted) arylthiazolyl butyramides were prepared by treating 2-amino-4-arylthiazole and 2-amino-4 (substituted) arylthiazoles with 4-chlorobutyrylchloride whereby 2-amino-4-aryl and 2-amino-4 (substituted) arylthiazolyl butyryl chlorides were obtained. These afforded the title compounds on subsequent treatment with various amines. The hydrochlorides of almost all the compounds screened have shown considerable local anaesthetic activity.

SOME derivatives of 2-aminothiazole^{1,2}, 2-amino-benzothiazoles³⁻⁶, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole⁶⁻⁸, 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole⁹ are reported to possess local anaesthetic activity. In continuation to our work on 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole⁶, we now report the synthesis of some new basic N-4-arylthiazolyl and N-4(substituted) arylthiazolyl butyramides as potential local anaesthetics by treating 2-amino-4-arylthiazole and 2-amino-4(substituted) arylthiazole with 4-chlorobutyryl chloride followed by condensation with various alkyl/aryl amines.

Experimental

Different 2-amino-4(substituted) arylthiazoles were prepared by known methods¹⁰.

2-Amino-4-arylthiazolyl butyryl chloride : Freshly distilled 4-chlorobutyryl chloride (5.7 ml) in dry benzene was gradually added to 2-amino-4-arylthiazole (8 g) dissolved in dry benzene containing potassium carbonate (4 g) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 2.5 hrs. Excess benzene was distilled off and the residue was treated with sodium bicarbonate and water to remove acid impurities. The product was recrystallized from ethanol.

Other thiazolyl butyryl chlorides were prepared similarly and are summarized in Table 1. These compounds were characterized on the basis of their elemental analysis and ir spectra. Purity of the compounds were also checked by tlc. The ir spectra have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer instrument in KBr, which showed characteristic absorption peaks in the region of 1655-1590 cm⁻¹ and 1360-1315 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O group and C-N bond respectively. In addition, all the compounds exhibited a strong band around 1720-1670 cm⁻¹ characteristics of the C-N group. Absorption band in

$\begin{array}{c} \parallel \\ \text{O} \end{array}$
the region of 3230-3160 cm⁻¹ indicated -NH-stretching frequency. The melting points were determined

on Toshniwal melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. The elemental analysis of the compound was carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and found to be consistent with the respective molecular formula.

N-dimethylamino-4-arylthiazolyl butyrimide : Dimethylamine (2.8 ml) in dry ethanol was gradually added to 2-amino-4-arylthiazolyl butyryl chloride (4 g) dissolved in dry ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hrs. Excess of ethanol and dimethylamine were recovered by distillation and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate and water respectively. The product was recrystallized from ethanol. M.P. 139°.

The other basic N-4-arylthiazolyl and N-4(substituted) arylthiazolyl butyramides were prepared similarly and the results have been tabulated in Tables 2 to 5. These compounds were characterized by ir spectra, m.p. and tlc. All the compounds were also analysed for N and S and gave satisfactory results.

The reaction may be depicted as

Biological activity : The preliminary investigations on the local anaesthetic activity of hydrochlorides of the above bases showed considerable activity in most of the compounds.

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TABLE 1—FORMATION OF 2-AMINO-4-ARYLTHIAZOLYL AND 2-AMINO-4-(SUBSTITUTED) ARYLTHIAZOLYL BUTYRYL CHLORIDES

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Yield %	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis			
					N%		S%	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	112	9.78	9.98	11.92	11.40
2.	p-chlorophenyl	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	124	8.64	8.88	10.28	10.15
3.	p-methylphenyl	74	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	85	9.72	9.50	10.72	10.86
4.	p-hydroxyphenyl	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	152	9.62	9.47	10.64	10.79

TABLE 2—FORMATION OF VARIOUS BASIC N-4-ARYLTHIAZOLYL BUTYRAMIDES

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁ R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula*	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
1.	Dimethyl	62	139	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	161
2.	Diethyl	58	142	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS	189-190
3.	Dipropyl	60	185	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ OS	185
4.	Diisopropyl	64	140	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ OS	181-182
5.	Morpholino	67	162	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	197
6.	Piperidino	59	150	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS	172
7.	Piperazino	72	146	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS	178-179
8.	Pyrrolidino	52	170	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	200
9.	Pyridine-2-	70	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	167-168
10.	Pyrimidine-2-	49	157	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	174

* All the compounds were analysed for N and S and gave satisfactory results.

TABLE 5—FORMATION OF VARIOUS BASIC N-4(p-HYDROXY) ARYLTHIAZOLYL BUTYRAMIDES

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁ R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
1.	Dimethyl	62	114	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	149
2.	Diethyl	59	91	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	187-188
3.	Dipropyl	68	126	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	201-202
4.	Diisopropyl	54	103	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	156
5.	Morpholino	62	129	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	210-211
6.	Piperidino	56	110	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	170-172
7.	Piperazino	48	87	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	146
8.	Pyrrolidino	66	83	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	142-143
9.	Pyridine-2-	52	120	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	198-199
10.	Pyrimidine-2-	57	95	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	154-155

TABLE 3—FORMATION OF VARIOUS BASIC N-4(p-CHLORO) ARYLTHIAZOLYL BUTYRAMIDES

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁ R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
1.	Dimethyl	67.0	143	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ OS	118-119
2.	Diethyl	55.0	170	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ OS	128
3.	Dipropyl	56.0	154	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ OS	141-142
4.	Diisopropyl	62.4	130	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ OS	109
5.	Morpholino	51.0	137	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	126-127
6.	Piperidine	53.6	151	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ OS	D*
7.	Piperazino	59.5	D	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₃ OS	D
8.	Pyrrolidino	63.0	148	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ OS	131
9.	Pyridine-2-	66.4	144	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ OS	112-113
10.	Pyrimidine-2-	61.0	179	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ OS	D

* Decomposed.

TABLE 4—FORMATION OF VARIOUS BASIC N-4(p-METHYL) ARYLTHIAZOLYL BUTYRAMIDES

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁ R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
1.	Dimethyl	87	119	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS	208-209
2.	Diethyl	59	95	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ OS	144-145
3.	Dipropyl	60	102	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ N ₂ OS	165
4.	Diisopropyl	58	106	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ N ₂ OS	199
5.	Morpholino	62	109	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	194
6.	Piperidino	60	105	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ OS	D
7.	Piperazino	63	98	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₃ OS	217-218
8.	Pyrrolidino	59	118	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ OS	203-204
9.	Pyridine-2-	57	111	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS	182
10.	Pyrimidine-2-	55	97	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	157-158

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